

Some q-Hypergeometric representations of the multiple Hurwitz zeta function

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Abstract

In this paper, The main object to give some new representations of the q-analogue of the multiple Hurwitz zeta function are derived.

Keywords: Multiple Hurwitz zeta function; q-Hypergeometric series; q-shifted factorial and special function.

1. Introduction, definitions and notations

The Hurwitz or generalized zeta function at integer points[13]

$$\zeta(s, a) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(n+a)^s}, \quad 0 < a \leq 1, \quad (1.1)$$

has a q-analogue defined by

$$\zeta_q(s, a) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^{(n+a)(s-1)}}{[n+a]_q^s}, \quad 0 < q < 1, \quad 0 < a \leq 1. \quad (1.2)$$

The series (1.2) is convergent for $\text{Re } s > 1$.

In [14] the q-analogue of Hurwitz zeta function is defined as

$$\zeta_q(s, a) = q^{a(s-1)} \{a\}_q^{-s} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} q^{-n} \left[\frac{\langle a; q \rangle_n}{\langle a+1; q \rangle_n} q^n \right]^s. \quad (1.3)$$

Barnes [4] (see also[1,2,3]) introduced and studied the generalized multiple Hurwitz zeta function $\zeta_n(s, a/w_1, \dots, w_n)$ defined, for $R(s) > n$, by the following series:

$$\zeta_n(s, a/w_1, \dots, w_n) = \sum_{k_1, \dots, k_n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(a + \Omega)^s} \quad (R(s)) > n ; n \in N , \quad (1.4)$$

where N denotes the set of positive integers $\Omega = k_1 w_1 + \dots + k_n w_n$.

Barnes-Changhee multiple q- zeta functions are defined by (see[9],[10]).

$$\zeta_{q,n}(s, w/a_1, a_2, \dots, a_r) = \sum_{n_1, \dots, n_n=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^{w+n_1+n_2+\dots+n_r}}{(w + n_1 a_1 + n_2 a_2 + \dots + n_r a_r)^s} \quad (1.5)$$

$R(w) > 0$, $q \in C$ with $|q| < 1$, which , for $a_1 = a_2 = \dots = a_r = 1$, yields

$$\zeta_{q,n}(s, w/1, 1, \dots, 1) = \sum_{n_1, \dots, n_n=0}^{\infty} \frac{q^{w+n_1+n_2+\dots+n_r}}{(w + n_1 + n_2 + \dots + n_r)^s}$$

Moreover, if $w = r$ and $s = 1 - n$ ($n \in Z^+$), we have

$$\zeta_{q,n}(n-1, r/1, 1, \dots, 1) = (-1)^r \frac{(n-1)!}{(n+r-1)!} B_{n+r-1}^{(r)}(r; q),$$

where $B_{n+r-1}^{(r)}(r; q)$ is called q-Bernoulli numbers.

We also note that

$$\lim_{q \rightarrow 1} \zeta_{q,n}(n-1, r/1, 1, \dots, 1) = \zeta_n(n-1, r/1, 1, \dots, 1) = (-1)^r \frac{(n-1)!}{(n+r-1)!} B_{n+r-1}^{(r)}(r)$$

(see[9],[10]).

Where the q-number $[z]_q$ is defined through

$$[z]_q = \frac{1 - q^z}{1 - q} , z \in C , q \neq 1. \quad (1.6)$$

A special case of (1.6) when $z \in N$ is $[n]_q = \frac{1 - q^n}{1 - q} = \sum_{0 \leq i \leq n-1} q^i , n \in N$

Which is called the q-analogue of $n \in N$, since

$$\lim_{q \rightarrow 1^-} [n]_q = \lim_{q \rightarrow 1^-} \sum_{0 \leq i \leq n-1} q^i = n.$$

The Pochhammer symbol $(\cdot)_k$, also called the shifted factorial, defined by

$$(z)_k = \prod_{j=0}^{k-1} (z+j), k \geq 1, (z)_0 = 1, (-z)_k = 0, \text{ if } z < k,$$

which in terms of the Gamma function is given by

$$(z)_k = \frac{\Gamma(z+k)}{\Gamma z}, k = 0,1,2,3,\dots, z \neq 0,-1,-2,\dots$$

And ${}_r F_s$ denoted the ordinary hypergeometric series ([4],[11]) with variable z is defined by

$${}_r F_s \left(\begin{matrix} a_1, \dots, a_r \\ b_1, \dots, b_s \end{matrix} / z \right) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(a_1, \dots, a_r)_k}{(b_1, \dots, b_s)_k} \frac{z^k}{k!}, \quad (1.7)$$

being $(a_1, \dots, a_r)_k = \prod_{i=1}^r (a_i)_k$, with $\{a_i\}_{i=1}^r$ and $\{b_j\}_{j=1}^s$ complex numbers subject to the condition that $b_j \neq -n$ with $n \in N - \{0\}$ for $j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, s$.

Here we will give some usual definitions and notations used in q-calculus, i.e. the q-analogues of the usual calculus.

Let the q-analogues of Pochhammer symbol or q-shifted factorial be defined by [5,7]

$$\langle a; q \rangle_n = \begin{cases} 1 & , n = 0 \\ \prod_{m=0}^{n-1} (1 - q^{a+m}) & , n = 1, 2, 3, \dots \end{cases} \quad (1.8)$$

The relation to Watson's notation, which is also included in the method, is $\langle a; q \rangle_n = (q^a; q)_n$ where

$$(a; q)_n = \begin{cases} 1 & , n = 0 \\ \prod_{m=0}^{n-1} (1 - aq^m) & , n = 1, 2, 3, \dots \end{cases}$$

and
$$\langle -n; q \rangle_k = \begin{cases} 0 & k > n \\ \frac{\langle 1; q \rangle_n}{\langle 1; q \rangle_{n-k}} (-1)^k q^{\binom{k}{2} - nk} & k \leq n \end{cases}, \quad (1.9)$$

also
$$\langle a; q \rangle_{n+k} = \langle a; q \rangle_n \langle aq^n; q \rangle_k \quad (1.10)$$

and
$$\lim_{q \rightarrow 1^-} \frac{(q^z; q)_k}{(1-q)^k} = (z)_k.$$

The q-binomial coefficient is defined by

$$\begin{bmatrix} n \\ k \end{bmatrix}_q = \frac{(q; q)_n}{(q; q)_k (q; q)_{n-k}} = \frac{\langle 1; q \rangle_n}{\langle 1; q \rangle_k \langle 1; q \rangle_{n-k}}, \quad 0 \leq k \leq n, \quad k, n \in \mathbb{N} \quad (1.11)$$

and for complex z is defined by

$$\begin{bmatrix} z \\ k \end{bmatrix}_q = \frac{(q^{-z}; q)_k}{(q; q)_k} (-1)^k q^{zk - \binom{k}{2}}; \quad k \in \mathbb{N} \quad (1.12)$$

Let $\{a_i\}_{i=1}^r$ and $\{b_j\}_{j=1}^s$ complex numbers subject to the condition that $b_j \neq q^{-n}$ with $n \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{0\}$ for $j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, s$.

Then the basic hypergeometric or q-hypergeometric ${}_r\phi_s$ series with variable z is defined by

$${}_r\phi_s \left(\begin{matrix} a_1, \dots, a_r \\ b_1, \dots, b_s \end{matrix} / q; z \right) = \sum_{k \geq 0} \frac{(a_1, \dots, a_r; q)_k}{(b_1, \dots, b_s; q)_k} (-1)^{(1+s-r)k} q^{(1+s-r)\binom{k}{2}} \frac{z^k}{(q; q)_k},$$

where $(a_1, \dots, a_r; q)_k = \prod_{1 \leq j \leq r} (a_j; q)_k$

In addition, for brevity, let us denote by

$$\left[{}_r\phi_s \left(\begin{matrix} a_1, \dots, a_r \\ b_1, \dots, b_s \end{matrix} / q; z \right) \right]^n = {}_r\phi_s^n \left(\begin{matrix} a_1, \dots, a_r \\ b_1, \dots, b_s \end{matrix} / q; z \right), \quad n = 1, 2, 3, \dots \quad (1.13)$$

Analogously to the ordinary hypergeometric ${}_{s+1}F_s$ series, the q-hypergeometric ${}_{s+1}\phi_s$ series is called k-balanced if $b_1 b_2 \dots b_s = q^k a_1 a_2 \dots a_{s+1}$.

The q-hypergeometric ${}_r\phi_s$ series is a q-analogue of the ordinary hypergeometric ${}_rF_s$ series defined by

$$\lim_{q \rightarrow 1^-} {}_r\phi_s \left(\begin{matrix} q^{a_1}, \dots, q^{a_r} \\ q^{b_1}, \dots, q^{b_s} \end{matrix} / q; z(q-1)^{1+s-r} \right) = {}_rF_s \left(\begin{matrix} a_1, \dots, a_r \\ b_1, \dots, b_s \end{matrix} / z \right).$$

Taking into account the following relations [14,p.18,19]

$${}_2\phi_1 \left[\begin{matrix} -n, b \\ c \end{matrix} / q; q^{n+c-b} \right] = \frac{\langle c-b; q \rangle_n}{\langle c; q \rangle_n}, \quad n = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots \quad (1.14)$$

where $\langle -n; q \rangle_k = 0$, whenever $n < k$,

and

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\langle a; q \rangle_n}{\langle 1; q \rangle_n} &= {}_2\phi_1 \left[\begin{matrix} -n, 1-a \\ 1 \end{matrix} / q; q^{n+a} \right] = \sum_{k \geq 0} \frac{\langle -n; q \rangle_k \langle 1-a; q \rangle_k}{\langle 1; q \rangle_k \langle 1; q \rangle_k} q^{k(n+a)} \\ &= \sum_{0 \leq k \leq n} \frac{\langle -n; q \rangle_k \langle 1-a; q \rangle_k}{\langle 1; q \rangle_k \langle 1; q \rangle_k} q^{k(n+a)} \end{aligned} \quad (1.15)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\langle 1; q \rangle_n}{\langle a+1; q \rangle_n} &= {}_2\phi_1 \left[\begin{matrix} -n, a \\ a+1 \end{matrix} / q; q^{n+1} \right] = \sum_{k \geq 0} \frac{\langle -n; q \rangle_k \langle a; q \rangle_k}{\langle 1; q \rangle_k \langle a+1; q \rangle_k} q^{k(n+1)} \\ &= \sum_{0 \leq k \leq n} \frac{\langle -n; q \rangle_k \langle a; q \rangle_k}{\langle 1; q \rangle_k \langle a+1; q \rangle_k} q^{k(n+1)} \end{aligned} \quad (1.16)$$

In [14] the following two relations are given by

$$\langle a; q \rangle_n = \langle a; q \rangle_{n+1} + q^{n+a} \langle a; q \rangle_n \quad (1.17)$$

$$\langle a; q \rangle_n = \langle 1; q \rangle_n \sum_{k=0}^n q^{(a+1)k} \frac{\langle -1; q \rangle_k \langle a+1; q \rangle_{n-k}}{\langle 1; q \rangle_k \langle 1; q \rangle_{n-k}}. \quad (1.18)$$

2. Main Results

In this section we establish some representations for the q-analogue of the multiple Hurwitz Zeta function which defined by

$$\zeta_n(s, w; q) = \sum_{r_1, \dots, r_n \geq 0} \frac{q^{(w+r_1+\dots+r_n)(s-1)}}{\{w+r_1+\dots+r_n\}_q^s}, \quad 0 < q < 1, \quad 0 < w \leq 1 \quad . \quad (2.1)$$

where $\{z\}_q$ denotes a q-analogue of a complex number defined by

$$\{z\}_q = \frac{1 - q^z}{1 - q}, \quad q \in \mathbb{C} \setminus \{1\}$$

The series (2.1) we can be rewritten as

$$\zeta_n(s, w; q) = q^{w(s-1)} \{w\}_q^{-s} \sum_{r_1, \dots, r_n \geq 0} \frac{\langle w; q \rangle_{r_1+\dots+r_n}^s}{\langle w+1; q \rangle_{r_1+\dots+r}^s} q^{(r_1+\dots+r)(s-1)}. \quad (2.2)$$

Theorem

Let s be an integer number, with $s > 1$, $|q| < 1$ and $0 < w \leq 1$. Then the q-analogue of the multiple Hurwitz zeta function (1.3), admits the following representations

$$\begin{aligned} \text{i. } \zeta_n(s, w; q) &= q^{w(s-1)} \{w\}_q^{-s} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-)^k q^{\binom{k}{2} + wk} {}_2\phi_1 \left[\begin{matrix} -k, 2w \\ w+1 \end{matrix} / q; q^{1-w+k} \right] {}_2\phi_1^{s-1} \left[\begin{matrix} -k, 1 \\ w+1 \end{matrix} / q; q \right] \\ & {}_{s+1}\phi_s \left[\begin{matrix} k+1, k+1, k+w, \dots, k+w \\ k+w+1, \dots, k+w+1 \end{matrix} / q; q^{s-1} \right] {}_{s+2}\phi_{s+1} \left[\begin{matrix} 1, k+1+r_1, k+1+r_1, k+w, \dots, k+w \\ 1+r_1, k+w+1, \dots, k+w+1 \end{matrix} / q; q^{s-1} \right] \\ & \dots {}_{s+2}\phi_{s+1} \left[\begin{matrix} 1, k+1+r_1+\dots+r_{n-1}, k+1+r_1+\dots+r_{n-1}, k+w+r_1+\dots+r_{n-1}, \dots, k+w+r_1+\dots+r_{n-1} \\ 1+r_1+\dots+r_{n-1}, k+w+1+r_1+\dots+r_{n-1}, \dots, k+w+1+r_1+\dots+r_{n-1} \end{matrix} / q; q^{s-1} \right], \end{aligned} \quad (2.3)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{ii. } \zeta_n(s, w; q) &= q^{w(s-1)} \{w\}_q^{-s} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-)^k q^{\binom{k}{2} + wk} {}_2\phi_1 \left[\begin{matrix} -k, 2w \\ w+1 \end{matrix} / q; q^{1-w+k} \right] {}_2\phi_1 \left[\begin{matrix} -k, 1-w \\ 1 \end{matrix} / q; q^{w+k} \right] \\ & {}_s\phi_{s-1} \left[\begin{matrix} k+w, \dots, k+w \\ k+w+1, \dots, k+w+1 \end{matrix} / q; q^{s-1} \right] {}_{s+1}\phi_s \left[\begin{matrix} 1, k+w, \dots, k+w \\ 1+r_1, k+w+1, \dots, k+w+1 \end{matrix} / q; q^{s-1} \right] \\ & \dots {}_{s+1}\phi_s \left[\begin{matrix} 1, k+w+r_1+\dots+r_{n-1}, \dots, k+w+r_1+\dots+r_{n-1} \\ 1+r_1+\dots+r_{n-1}, k+w+1+r_1+\dots+r_{n-1}, \dots, k+w+1+r_1+\dots+r_{n-1} \end{matrix} / q; q^{s-1} \right], \end{aligned} \quad (2.4)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{iii. } \zeta_n(s, w; q) &= q^{w(s-1)} \{w\}_q^{-s} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} q^{(w+1)k} {}_2\phi_1 \left[\begin{matrix} -k, w+2 \\ w+1 \end{matrix} / q; q^{k-1} \right] {}_2\phi_1^{s-1} \left[\begin{matrix} -k, 1 \\ w+1 \end{matrix} / q; q \right] \\
 & {}_{s+1}\phi_s \left[\begin{matrix} k+1, w+1, k+w, \dots, k+w \\ k+w+1, \dots, k+w+1 \end{matrix} / q; q^{s-1} \right] {}_{s+2}\phi_{s+1} \left[\begin{matrix} 1, k+1+r_1, k+1+r_1, k+w+r_1, \dots, k+w+r_1 \\ 1+r_1, k+w+1+r_1, \dots, k+w+1+r_1 \end{matrix} / q; q^{s-1} \right] \\
 & \dots {}_{s+2}\phi_{s+1} \left[\begin{matrix} 1, k+1+r_1+\dots+r_{n-1}, k+1+r_1+\dots+r_{n-1}, k+w+r_1+\dots+r_{n-1}, \dots, k+w+r_1+\dots+r_{n-1} \\ 1+r_1+\dots+r_{n-1}, k+w+1+r_1+\dots+r_{n-1}, \dots, k+w+1+r_1+\dots+r_{n-1} \end{matrix} / q; q^{s-1} \right], \tag{2.5}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{iv. } \zeta_n(s, w; q) &= (1-q^w) q^{w(s-1)} \{w\}_q^{-s} {}_s\phi_{s-1} \left[\begin{matrix} 1, w, \dots, w \\ w+1, \dots, w+1 \end{matrix} / q; q^s \right] \\
 & {}_s\phi_{s-1} \left[\begin{matrix} 1, w+r_1, \dots, w+r_1 \\ w+1+r_1, \dots, w+1+r_1 \end{matrix} / q; q^s \right] \dots {}_s\phi_{s-1} \left[\begin{matrix} 1, w+r_1+\dots+r_{n-1}, \dots, w+r_1+\dots+r_{n-1} \\ w+1+r_1+\dots+r_{n-1}, \dots, w+1+r_1+\dots+r_{n-1} \end{matrix} / q; q^s \right] \\
 & + q^{ws} \{w\}_q^{-s} {}_{s+1}\phi_s \left[\begin{matrix} 1, w, \dots, w \\ w+1, \dots, w+1 \end{matrix} / q; q^s \right] \dots {}_{s+1}\phi_s \left[\begin{matrix} 1, w+r_1+\dots+r_{n-1}, \dots, w+r_1+\dots+r_{n-1} \\ w+1+r_1+\dots+r_{n-1}, \dots, w+1+r_1+\dots+r_{n-1} \end{matrix} / q; q^s \right]. \tag{2.6}
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof.

From (2.2) and using relation (1.15), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 \zeta_n(s, w; q) &= q^{w(s-1)} \{w\}_q^{-s} \sum_{r_1, \dots, r_n \geq 0} \frac{\langle w; q \rangle_{r_1+\dots+r_n}^{s-1} \langle 1; q \rangle_{r_1+\dots+r_n}}{\langle w+1; q \rangle_{r_1+\dots+r}^s} q^{(r_1+\dots+r_n)(s-1)} \\
 & \times \sum_{0 \leq k \leq r_1, \dots, r_n} \frac{\langle -(r_1+\dots+r_n); q \rangle_k \langle 1-w; q \rangle_k}{\langle 1; q \rangle_k \langle 1; q \rangle_k} q^{k((r_1+\dots+r_n)+w)}
 \end{aligned}$$

Then, using (1,9) with replacing n by $r_1 + r_2 + \dots + r_n$, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 \zeta_n(s, w; q) &= q^{w(s-1)} \{w\}_q^{-s} \sum_{k \geq 0} \sum_{r_1, \dots, r_n \geq 0} \frac{\langle w; q \rangle_{r_1+\dots+r_n+k}^{s-1} \langle 1-w; q \rangle_k \langle 1; q \rangle_{r_1+\dots+r_n+k} \langle 1; q \rangle_{r_1+\dots+r_n+k}}{\langle w+1; q \rangle_{r_1+\dots+r_n+k}^s \langle 1; q \rangle_k \langle 1; q \rangle_k \langle 1; q \rangle_{r_1+\dots+r_n}} \\
 & \times (-q^w)^k q^{\binom{k}{2} + (r_1+\dots+r_n+k)(s-1)} \\
 & = q^{w(s-1)} \{w\}_q^{-s} \sum_{k \geq 0} (-1)^k q^{\binom{k}{2} + wk} \frac{\langle 1-w; q \rangle_k}{\langle w+1; q \rangle_k} \frac{\langle w; q \rangle_k^{s-1}}{\langle w+1; q \rangle_k^{s-1}} q^{k(s-1)} \\
 & \times \sum_{r_1, \dots, r_n \geq 0} \frac{\langle 1+k; q \rangle_{r_1+\dots+r_n} \langle 1+k; q \rangle_{r_1+\dots+r_n} \langle k+w; q \rangle_{r_1+\dots+r_n}^{s-1}}{\langle 1; q \rangle_{r_1+\dots+r_n} \langle k+w+1; q \rangle_{r_1+\dots+r_n}^s} q^{(r_1+\dots+r_n)(s-1)}
 \end{aligned}$$

By using relation (1.14), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= q^{w(s-1)} \{w\}_q^{-s} \sum_{k \geq 0} (-1)^k q^{\binom{k}{2} + wk} {}_2\phi_1 \left[\begin{matrix} -k, 2w \\ w+1 \end{matrix} / q; q^{1-w+k} \right] {}_2\phi_1^{s-1} \left[\begin{matrix} -k, 1 \\ w+1 \end{matrix} / q; q \right] \\
 &\quad \times \sum_{r_1 \geq 0} \frac{\langle 1+k; q \rangle_{r_1} \langle 1+k; q \rangle_{r_1} \langle k+w; q \rangle_{r_1}^{s-1}}{\langle 1; q \rangle_{r_1} \langle k+w+1; q \rangle_{r_1}^s} q^{r_1(s-1)} \\
 &\quad \times \sum_{r_2 \geq 0} \frac{\langle 1+k+r_1; q \rangle_{r_2} \langle 1+k+r_1; q \rangle_{r_2} \langle k+w+r_1; q \rangle_{r_2}^{s-1}}{\langle 1+r_1; q \rangle_{r_2} \langle k+w+1+r_1; q \rangle_{r_2}^s} q^{r_2(s-1)} \\
 &\quad \vdots \\
 &\quad \times \sum_{r_n \geq 0} \frac{\langle 1+k+r_1+\dots+r_{n-1}; q \rangle_{r_n} \langle 1+k+r_1+\dots+r_{n-1}; q \rangle_{r_n} \langle k+w+r_1+\dots+r_{n-1}; q \rangle_{r_n}^{s-1}}{\langle 1+r_1+\dots+r_{n-1}; q \rangle_{r_n} \langle k+w+1+r_1+\dots+r_{n-1}; q \rangle_{r_n}^s} q^{r_n(s-1)}
 \end{aligned}$$

which is required (2.3).

Similarly, From (2.2) and the relation (1.16) with replacing n by $r_1 + r_2 + \dots + r_n$ we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 \zeta_n(s, w; q) &= q^{w(s-1)} \{w\}_q^{-s} \sum_{r_1, \dots, r_n \geq 0} \frac{\langle w; q \rangle_{r_1+\dots+r_n}^s q^{(r_1+\dots+r_n)(s-1)}}{\langle w+1; q \rangle_{r_1+\dots+r_n}^{s-1} \langle 1; q \rangle_{r_1+\dots+r_n}} \\
 &\quad \times \sum_{0 \leq k \leq r_1, \dots, r_n} \frac{\langle -(r_1+\dots+r_n); q \rangle_k \langle w; q \rangle_k}{\langle 1; q \rangle_k \langle w+1; q \rangle_k} q^{k(r_1+\dots+r_n+1)} \\
 \zeta_n(s, w; q) &= q^{w(s-1)} \{w\}_q^{-s} \sum_{k \geq 0} (-1)^k q^{\binom{k+1}{2}} \frac{\langle w; q \rangle_k \langle w; q \rangle_k \langle w; q \rangle_k^{s-1}}{\langle w+1; q \rangle_k \langle 1; q \rangle_k \langle w+1; q \rangle_k^{s-1}} q^{k(s-1)} \\
 &\quad \times \sum_{r_1, \dots, r_n \geq 0} \frac{\langle k+w; q \rangle_{r_1+\dots+r_n}^s}{\langle 1; q \rangle_{r_1+\dots+r_n} \langle k+w+1; q \rangle_{r_1+\dots+r_n}^{s-1}} q^{(r_1+\dots+r_n+k)(s-1)}
 \end{aligned}$$

Which by using relation (1.14), we find

$$\begin{aligned} \zeta_n(s, w; q) &= q^{w(s-1)} \{w\}_q^{-s} \\ &\times \sum_{k \geq 0} (-1)^k q^{\binom{k+1}{2}} {}_2\phi_1 \left[\begin{matrix} -k, 1 \\ w+1 \end{matrix} / q; q^{k+w} \right] {}_2\phi_1 \left[\begin{matrix} -k, 1-w \\ 1 \end{matrix} / q; q^{k+w} \right] {}_2\phi_1^{s-1} \left[\begin{matrix} -k, 1 \\ w+1 \end{matrix} / q; q \right] \\ &\times \sum_{r_1 \geq 0} \frac{\langle k+w; q \rangle_{r_1}^s}{\langle 1; q \rangle_{r_1} \langle k+w+1; q \rangle_{r_1}^{s-1}} q^{r_1(s-1)} \sum_{r_2 \geq 0} \frac{\langle k+w+r_1; q \rangle_{r_2}^s}{\langle 1+r_1; q \rangle_{r_1} \langle k+w+1+r_1; q \rangle_{r_2}^{s-1}} q^{r_2(s-1)} \\ &\vdots \\ &\times \sum_{r_n \geq 0} \frac{\langle k+w+r_1+\dots+r_{n-1}; q \rangle_{r_n}^s}{\langle 1+r_1+\dots+r_{n-1}; q \rangle_{r_n} \langle k+w+1+r_1+\dots+r_{n-1}; q \rangle_{r_n}^{s-1}} q^{r_n(s-1)} \end{aligned}$$

which is required (2.4).

Now, by using expression (1.18) in (2.2), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \zeta_n(s, w; q) &= q^{w(s-1)} \{w\}_q^{-s} \sum_{k \geq 0} \sum_{r_1, \dots, r_n \geq 0} \frac{\langle w; q \rangle_{r_1+\dots+r_n+k}^{s-1} \langle 1; q \rangle_{r_1+\dots+r_n+k}}{\langle w+1; q \rangle_{r_1+\dots+r_n+k}^s \langle 1; q \rangle_k} \\ &\times (q)^{(w+1)k} \frac{\langle -1; q \rangle_k \langle w+1; q \rangle_{r_1+\dots+r_n}}{\langle 1; q \rangle_{r_1+\dots+r_n}} q^{(r_1+\dots+r_n+k)(s-1)} \end{aligned}$$

By using expression (1.10), we find

$$\begin{aligned} \zeta_n(s, w; q) &= q^{w(s-1)} \{w\}_q^{-s} \sum_{k \geq 0} (q)^{(w+1)k} \frac{\langle -1; q \rangle_k \langle 1; q \rangle_k \langle w; q \rangle_k^{s-1}}{\langle w+1; q \rangle_k \langle 1; q \rangle_k \langle w+1; q \rangle_k^{s-1}} q^{k(s-1)} \\ &\times \sum_{r_1, \dots, r_n \geq 0} \frac{\langle 1+k; q \rangle_{r_1+\dots+r_n} \langle w+1; q \rangle_{r_1+\dots+r_n} \langle w+k; q \rangle_{r_1+\dots+r_n}^{s-1}}{\langle 1; q \rangle_{r_1+\dots+r_n} \langle w+1+k; q \rangle_{r_1+\dots+r_n}^s} q^{(r_1+\dots+r_n)(s-1)} \end{aligned}$$

By using relation (1.14), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \zeta_n(s, w; q) &= q^{w(s-1)} \{w\}_q^{-s} \sum_{k \geq 0} (q)^{(w+1)k} {}_2\phi_1 \left[\begin{matrix} -k, w+2 \\ w+1 \end{matrix} / q; q^{k-1} \right] {}_2\phi_1^{s-1} \left[\begin{matrix} -k, 1 \\ w+1 \end{matrix} / q; q \right] \\ &\times \sum_{r_1 \geq 0} \frac{\langle 1+k; q \rangle_{r_1} \langle w+1; q \rangle_{r_1} \langle w+k; q \rangle_{r_1}^{s-1}}{\langle 1; q \rangle_{r_1} \langle w+1+k; q \rangle_{r_1}^s} q^{r_1(s-1)} \\ &\times \sum_{r_2 \geq 0} \frac{\langle 1+k+r_1; q \rangle_{r_2} \langle w+1+r_1; q \rangle_{r_2} \langle w+k+r_1; q \rangle_{r_2}^{s-1}}{\langle 1+r_1; q \rangle_{r_2} \langle w+1+k+r_1; q \rangle_{r_2}^s} q^{(r_2)(s-1)} \\ &\vdots \end{aligned}$$

$$\times \sum_{r_n \geq 0} \frac{\langle 1+k+r_1+\dots+r_{n-1}; q \rangle_{r_n} \langle w+1+r_1+\dots+r_{n-1}; q \rangle_{r_n} \langle w+k+r_1+\dots+r_{n-1}; q \rangle_{r_n}^{s-1}}{\langle 1+r_1+\dots+r_{n-1}; q \rangle_{r_n} \langle w+1+k+r_1+\dots+r_{n-1}; q \rangle_{r_n}^s} q^{(r_n)(s-1)}$$

which is required (2.5).

Finally, using relation (1.17) in (2.2), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \zeta_n(s, w; q) &= q^{w(s-1)} \{w\}_q^{-s} \sum_{r_1, \dots, r_n \geq 0} \frac{\langle w; q \rangle_{r_1+\dots+r_n}^{s-1} \langle w; q \rangle_{r_1+\dots+r_n+1}}{\langle w+1; q \rangle_{r_1+\dots+r_n}^{s-1} \langle w+1; q \rangle_{r_1+\dots+r_n}} q^{(r_1+\dots+r_n)(s-1)} \\ &\quad + q^{ws} \{w\}_q^{-s} \sum_{r_1, \dots, r_n \geq 0} \frac{\langle w; q \rangle_{r_1+\dots+r_n}^s}{\langle w+1; q \rangle_{r_1+\dots+r_n}^s} q^{(r_1+\dots+r_n)s} \end{aligned}$$

since $\langle w+1; q \rangle_{r_1+\dots+r_n} = \frac{1-q^{r_1+\dots+r_n+w}}{1-q^w} \langle w; q \rangle_{r_1+\dots+r_n}$

and $\langle w+1; q \rangle_{r_1+\dots+r_n+1} = \langle 1-q^{r_1+\dots+r_n+w} \rangle \langle w; q \rangle_{r_1+\dots+r_n}$

we deduce

$$\begin{aligned} \zeta_n(s, w; q) &= (1-q^w) q^{w(s-1)} \{w\}_q^{-s} \sum_{r_1, \dots, r_n \geq 0} \frac{\langle w; q \rangle_{r_1+\dots+r_n}^{s-1}}{\langle w+1; q \rangle_{r_1+\dots+r_n}^{s-1}} q^{(r_1+\dots+r_n)(s-1)} \\ &\quad + q^{ws} \{w\}_q^{-s} \sum_{r_1, \dots, r_n \geq 0} \frac{\langle w; q \rangle_{r_1+\dots+r_n}^s}{\langle w+1; q \rangle_{r_1+\dots+r_n}^s} q^{(r_1+\dots+r_n)s} \end{aligned}$$

By using relation (1.10), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \zeta_n(s, w; q) &= (1-q^w) q^{w(s-1)} \{w\}_q^{-s} \sum_{r_1 \geq 0} \frac{\langle w; q \rangle_{r_1}^{s-1}}{\langle w+1; q \rangle_{r_1}^{s-1}} q^{(r_1)(s-1)} \sum_{r_2 \geq 0} \frac{\langle w+r_1; q \rangle_{r_2}^{s-1}}{\langle w+1+r_1; q \rangle_{r_2}^{s-1}} q^{(r_2)(s-1)} \\ &\quad \dots \sum_{r_n \geq 0} \frac{\langle w+r_1+\dots+r_{n-1}; q \rangle_{r_n}^{s-1}}{\langle w+1+r_1+\dots+r_{n-1}; q \rangle_{r_n}^{s-1}} q^{(r_n)(s-1)} \\ &\quad + q^{ws} \{w\}_q^{-s} \sum_{r_1 \geq 0} \frac{\langle w; q \rangle_{r_1}^s}{\langle w+1; q \rangle_{r_1}^s} q^{(r_1)s} \sum_{r_2 \geq 0} \frac{\langle w+r_1; q \rangle_{r_2}^s}{\langle w+1+r_1; q \rangle_{r_2}^s} q^{(r_2)s} \\ &\quad \dots \sum_{r_n \geq 0} \frac{\langle w+r_1+\dots+r_{n-1}; q \rangle_{r_n}^s}{\langle w+1+r_1+\dots+r_{n-1}; q \rangle_{r_n}^s} q^{(r_n)s} \end{aligned}$$

which is required (2.6).

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